

Prevalence of Internet Addiction and Its Association with Psychopathology among Medical Students in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Northern KeralaArun Kumar S.¹, Yesudas Kalathara Francis², Sumesh Balachandran.³¹Junior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Kannur, Kerala, India²HOD, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Kannur, Kerala, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Kannur, Kerala, India

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Abstract

Background: Overuse of the internet exacerbates emotional instability, stress, anxiety, and depression among medical students who are already susceptible due to pressure of performing well academically. Internet use and its association with psychopathology can be studied by using DASS-42 (Depression Anxiety Stress Scale – 42). Our aim was to assess the prevalence of internet addiction and its association with psychopathology among medical students in a tertiary care hospital.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted among 400 MBBS students to determine the prevalence of internet addiction and its associated psychopathology over a period of 1 year. Assessment was made using internet addiction test [Young], the DASS-42 and socio-demographic proforma. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS version. Internet addiction was expressed as frequency and percentage. Socio-demographic values were expressed as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and median. Prevalence of internet addiction and its associated psychopathology was assessed using chi square test. Probability value 'p' < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The prevalence of internet addiction among MBBS students was 52.75%. 33.75% had mild addiction, 12% had moderate addiction, and 7% had severe addiction. The prevalence of internet addiction was greater among females (54.16%) compared to males (50%). A higher prevalence of internet addiction was observed in the 22-year age group (61.4%). Students struggling with internet addiction exhibited symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress, and there was a significant correlation between internet addiction and these mental health issues.

Conclusion: There was a significant association between internet addiction and psychopathology (depression, anxiety, and stress) among medical students. Proactive awareness campaigns, possibly launched by academic institutions are necessary to educate medical students about the significance of limiting excessive internet use and tackling the root causes.

Keywords: Internet Addiction, Medical Students, Psychopathology.

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Introduction

India is the second-largest internet market in the world, with 700 million users, and has experienced exponential growth, rising from 4 percent in 2007 to 47 percent currently.[1,2] However, research has shown that it may be abused and result in addiction and pose an unseen risk to sleep and mental health.[3] Overuse of the internet exacerbates emotional instability, stress, anxiety, and depression among medical students who are already susceptible due to pressure of performing well academically.[4] There is an urgent need to pay attention to the internet addiction that is hurting the psychological well-being of medical students, who are our society's most valuable future physicians.

Internet use and its association with psychopathology can be studied by using DASS-42.

Loviband and Loviband developed this DASS-42 scale. This is a 42-item questionnaire containing 14 questions for each subscale, i.e., depression [14 items], anxiety [14 items], and stress [14 items]. The depression scale assesses hopelessness, self-deprecation, anhedonia, devaluation of life, dysphoria, lack of interest/involvement, and inertia. The anxiety scale focuses on autonomic arousal, situational anxiety, skeletal muscle effects, and subjective experience of any anxious effect. The stress scale assesses the magnitude of tension and irritability. A number of studies across the world have studied internet addiction, especially among adolescents.

Research specifically on internet addiction and its association with psychopathology among medical

students is relatively new and limited. The present study is an attempt to find the prevalence of internet addiction and its association with psychopathology among undergraduate medical students so that preventive and therapeutic interventions can be recommended.

Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted among 400 MBBS students to determine the prevalence of internet addiction and its associated psychopathology over a period of 1 year. Assessment was made with internet addiction test [Young], the DASS-42

and socio-demographic proforma. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS version. Internet addiction was expressed as frequency and percentage. Socio-demographic values were expressed as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and median. The prevalence of internet addiction and its associated psychopathology was assessed using chi-square test. Probability value 'p' < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The mean age of the student group was 21.99±1.47 years. Higher number of students belonged to 21 years (30%) as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Age Distribution of the Students and Their Percentages

Age Distribution	Number	Percentage (%)
20 Years	66	16.5
21 Years	120	30
22 Years	70	17.5
23 Years	51	12.75
24 Years	80	20
25 Years	13	3.25
Mean Age	21.99±1.47	

A higher number of female students was observed (65.75%) in this study. 98.25% were unmarried. Out of 500 students, 284 had a nuclear family, 88 had a joint family, and 28 had an extended family. Out of 500 students, 106 were rural students, 200 were semi-urban students, and 94 were urban students. A higher number of students was above the poverty line (82.75%). 76.25% had no family histo-

ry of psychiatric illness. Family history of substance use was seen in 12.75%, anxiety disorder (6%), and depression (3.25%).

The internet addiction score of the students and their percentages are as shown in Figure 1. A higher number of students had a normal level (47.25%), followed by mild-level students (33.75%) and severe-level students (7%).

Figure 1: Comparison of the Internet Addiction Score of the Students and Their Percentages

In all the age groups, a higher number of students with normal scores was observed, followed by mild addiction. The p-value (0.222) was not statistically

significant. The prevalence rate of internet addiction was higher in females (54.16%) than in males

(50%), but the p-value (0.706) was not statistically significant. With respect to the prevalence of depression, a higher number of normal students was observed

(56%), followed by mild depression students (31.5%) and very few extremely severe depression students (2.5%) were observed.

Figure 2: Comparison of the Depression of the Students and Their Percentages

With respect to the prevalence of anxiety, a higher number of normal students was observed (51.25%), followed by mild anxiety students (34.25%); very

few extremely severe anxiety students (2.75%) were observed.

Figure 3: Comparison of the Anxiety of the Students and Their Percentages

With respect to the prevalence of stress, a higher number of normal students was observed (43%), followed by students having a mild level of stress

(39%); very few students with extremely severe stress (1.75%) were observed.

Figure 4: Comparison of the Stress of the Students and Their Percentages

Among internet addiction students, the higher number of depressed students (156) and few normal students (55) were observed. The p-value (0.0001) was statistically significant.

A higher number of anxiety students (154) and few normal students (57) were observed. The p-value (0.0001) was statistically significant. A higher number of stressed students (175) and few normal patients (36) were observed. The p-value (0.0001) was statistically significant.

The correlation between internet addiction score and depression was statistically significant, $r(397) = 0.86$, $p < .001$. The correlation between internet addiction score and anxiety score was also statistically significant, $r(398) = 0.78$, $p < .001$. The correlation between internet addiction score and stress was statistically significant, $r(398) = 0.73$, $p < .001$. Table 2 and Figures 5, 6, and 7.

Table 2: Correlation Co-Efficient of the Internet Addiction

Internet Addiction	Depression	Anxiety	Stress
Correlation Coefficient	0.86	0.78	0.73
P-Value	0.001	0.001	0.001

Figure 5: Correlation between the Internet Addiction Score and Depression of the Students

Figure 6: Correlation between the Internet Addiction Score and Anxiety Score of the Students

Figure 7: Correlation between the Internet Addiction Score and Stress of the Students

Discussion

This cross-sectional study was conducted among MBBS students to determine the prevalence of internet addiction and its associated psychopathology over a period of 1 year. It has been documented through various studies and literature that internet addiction in India is on the rise (Tadpatrikar et al. [5], Joseph J. et al. [6]) and its association with depression, anxiety, and stress among MBBS students is increasing gradually (Rani et al. [7], Iniyar et al. [8]). A better understanding of the relationship between internet addiction and its association with psychopathology would enable us to understand the pattern better and plan for specific strategies to prevent internet addiction and its consequences.

Prevalence of Internet Addiction

The prevalence of internet addiction among medical students in the present study was 52.75%. Within this group, 33.75% had mild addiction, 12% had moderate addiction, and a small percentage (7%) had severe addiction. i et al., [9] Mashaei et al., [10] Raveendran R et al. [11], and Traore B., Aguilo Y., Hassoune S., et al. [12]

The rising prevalence over the past few years could be attributed to technological advancements, which have made internet access more affordable and accessible for students, thereby increasing their dependence on it.

Furthermore, this prevalence rate was significantly higher compared to those reported in research involving medical students from Saudi Arabia and Pakistan, where prevalences were 12.4% and 7.86%, respectively (Mohamed H. Taha et al., [13] J Ayub et al. [14])

Some studies have reported higher prevalence rates of internet addiction among medical students compared to those observed in our study (Athulya et al. [15] Kumari et al. [16]). Research investigating the association between religiosity and internet addiction in adolescents and young adults suggests that religiosity may serve as a protective factor, with lower levels of internet addiction associated with higher religiosity. The Muslim population in Northern Kerala is higher compared to that in Southern Kerala and other states of India. This demographic difference may partly explain why the prevalence rate in our study is lower than that reported in the aforementioned studies.

Sociodemographic Profile

The prevalence rate of internet addiction was higher in females (54.16%) than in males (50%), but the difference was not statistically significant (p-value of 0.706). This higher prevalence among females has been observed in various other studies focused on medical students (Mashaei et al., [17] Mohamed H. Taha et al. [13]) In our study, women likely use social networking platforms more frequently than men, and this higher usage was associated with increased internet addiction. In contrast to our study, numerous studies have documented a higher prevalence of internet addiction among male students, both in India and internationally. (Goel D et al. [18] Waldo AD et al. [19])

A higher prevalence of internet addiction was observed in the 22-year age group (61.4%), but with a p-value of 0.222, this result was not statistically significant. Therefore, we found no significant association between the age of the study participants and internet addiction. Similar results regarding age and internet addiction have been reported in studies from India (Krishnamurthy S, [19]) as well as from other countries. (Tsitsika A et al. [20]).

Internet Addiction and Its Association with Psychopathology

Among those with internet addiction, 73.93% had depressive symptoms. These findings are consistent with those of Rani et al., [7] Iniyan et al., [8] and Rashmi R et al., [22] all of whom observed a strong positive association between internet addiction and depression. Individuals with depression may find online communication more accessible and less intimidating compared to face-to-face interactions due to the anonymity, lack of nonverbal cues, and absence of physical presence. These aspects can help them manage their interpersonal challenges, which are commonly associated with depression. As a result, they might turn to the internet excessively to alleviate their low mood and escape feelings of guilt and hopelessness (Gupta et al). 72.98% had anxiety symptoms. These findings align with studies by Rani et al. [7], Iniyan et al., [8] Carli et al., [23] all of which reported a strong positive association between internet addiction and anxiety. Studies conducted outside India have also found a link between anxiety and the risk of IA (Internet Addiction). (Younes F [24], Kawabe K et al. [25]) Individuals with internet addiction may experience heightened anxiety both as a withdrawal symptom and due to comorbid depression. People with anxiety might resort to excessive internet use as a coping mechanism to alleviate their dysphoric mood.

Among those with internet addiction, 82.93% had stress symptoms. These findings were also found to be comparable to studies done by Saikia et al., [18] Rani et al., [7] Iniyan et al., [8] Carli et al., [23] and Rashmi R et al. [22] where they found a strong positive association between internet addiction and stress. Individuals with an avoidant coping style may begin using the internet excessively to escape stress from real-world issues, potentially leading to addiction. (Gupta, et al. [26])

Considering these findings, it is likely that individuals with internet addiction face an increased risk of developing psychopathological conditions. Alternatively, there is also a possibility that existing psychopathology might contribute to the onset of internet addiction. To the best of our knowledge, this is one of the few studies that has evaluated the association between internet addiction and its psychopathology among medical students in South India. However, as the study was conducted in a single centre, the results cannot be generalized to the medical student population.

Conclusion

There was a significant association between internet addiction and psychopathology (depression, anxiety and stress) among medical students. Proactive awareness campaigns, possibly launched by academic institutions, are necessary to educate medical

students about the significance of limiting excessive internet use and tackling the root causes.

Strengths

To the best of our knowledge, ours was one of the few studies that has evaluated the association between internet addiction and its psychopathology among medical students in South India. The study's sample size was ample enough to offer basic information regarding internet addiction within the medical student population.

Limitations

This study was conducted in a single centre and hence the results cannot be generalized to the medical student population. We are unable to determine the temporal associations or causal relationships between internet addiction and depression, anxiety, and stress because cross-sectional studies, while useful for identifying associations, do not provide insights into causal relationships between internet addiction and specific psychopathological disorders.

References

1. Basuroy T. Internet penetration rate in India 2007-2021. Statista Research Department.
2. Pan YC, Chiu YC, Lin YH. Systematic review and meta-analysis of epidemiology of internet addiction. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev* 2020; 118:612-22.
3. Shapira NA, Goldsmith TD, Keck PE, Jr, Khosla UM, McElroy SL. Psychiatric features of individuals with problematic internet use. *J Affect Disord* 2000; 57:267-72.
4. Chen YL, Gau SSF. Sleep problems and Internet addiction among children and adolescents: A longitudinal study. *J Sleep Res* 2016; 25:458-65.
5. Tadpatrikar A, Sharma MK, Amudhan S, Desai G. The prevalence and correlates of internet addiction in India as assessed by young's internet addiction test: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine* 2024;46(6).
6. Joseph J, Varghese A, Vijay VR, Dhandapani M, Grover S, Sharma S, et al. Prevalence of internet addiction among college students in the Indian setting: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Gen Psychiatr* 2021;34(4): e100496.
7. Rani S, Sinha N, Kumar R. Prevalence of internet addiction and its relationship with insomnia, depression, anxiety, and stress among medical students at a tertiary care medical institute of Eastern India. *Ind Psychiatry J* 2024;33(1):94100.
8. Selvamani I, Natarajan V, Ahamed KF, Krishnan R. Prevalence of internet addiction and its association with depression, anxiety and stress

- in medical students during the Covid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results* 2022;13(9):4102-07.
9. Chaudhari B, Menon P, Saldanha D, Tewari A, Bhattacharya L. Internet addiction and its determinants among medical students. *Industrial Psychiatry Journal* 2015;24(2):158-62.
 10. Naffise M, Mohammad A, Ahmad PB, Omid R, Ayatollahi A, Reza B, et al. The prevalence of Internet addiction among the students of Rafsanjan University of Medical Sciences. *ASEAN J Psychiatry* 2013;14(2):109-6.
 11. Raveendran R, Jose R, Jacob SR, George AS, Vinayak N, Muhyudheen KM, et al. Internet usage among medical students: prevalence, addiction, and health issues. *International Journal of Community Medicine And Public Health* 2021;8(8):4030-6.
 12. Traore B, Aguilo Y, Hassoune S, Nani S. Determinants of internet addiction among medical students in Casablanca: a cross-sectional study. *Global Health Journal* 2023;7(2):101-9.
 13. Taha MH, Shehzad K, Alamro AS, Wadi M. Internet use and addiction among medical students in Qassim University, Saudi Arabia. *Sultan Qaboos Univ Med J* 2019;19(2):e142-7.
 14. Haroon MZ, Zeb Z, Javed Z, Awan Z, Aftab Z, Talat W. Internet addiction in medical students. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad* 2018;30(4): S659-63.
 15. Asokan AG, Varghese VA, Rajeev A. Internet addiction among medical students and its impact on academic performance: an Indian study. *J Med Sci Clin Res* 2019;7(3):670.
 16. Kumari R, Langer B, Gupta R, Gupta RK, Mir MT, Shafi B, et al. Prevalence and determinants of Internet addiction among the students of professional colleges in the Jammu region. *J Family Med Prim Care* 2022;11(1):325-9.
 17. Naffise M, Mohammad A, Ahmad PB, Omid R, Ayatollahi A, Reza B, Fatemeh AB. The prevalence of Internet addiction among the students of Rafsanjan University of Medical Sciences. *ASEAN J Psychiatry* 2013;14(2):109-6.
 18. Goel D, Subramanyam A, Kamath R. A study on the prevalence of internet addiction and its association with psychopathology in Indian adolescents. *Indian J Psychiatry* 2013; 55:140-3.
 19. Waldo AD. Correlates of internet addiction among adolescents. *Psychology* 2014;5(18):1999-2008.
 20. Krishnamurthy S, Chetlapalli SK. Internet addiction: prevalence and risk factors: a cross-sectional study among college students in Bengaluru, the Silicon Valley of India. *Indian J Public Health* 2015; 59:115-21.
 21. Tsitsika A, Janikian M, Schoenmakers TM, Tzavela EC, Olafsson K, Wójcik S, et al. Internet addictive behavior in adolescence: a cross-sectional study in seven European countries. *Cyberpsychol Behav Soc Netw* 2014; 17:528-35.
 22. Rashmi R, Harsha GT, Khargekar VC, Karthik KN, Narayanaswamy DM. The internet addiction pattern and its mental impact among medical students in Bangalore: a cross-sectional study. *National Journal of Community Medicine* 2022;13(07):458-62.
 23. Carli V, Durkee T, Wasserman D, Hadlaczky G, Despalins R, Kramarz E, et al. The association between pathological internet use and comorbid psychopathology: a systematic review. *Psychopathology* 2013;46(1):1-13.
 24. Younes F, Halawi G, Jabbour H, El Osta N, Karam L, Hajj A, et al. Internet addiction and relationships with insomnia, anxiety, depression, stress and self-esteem in university students: A Cross-sectional designed study. *PLoS One* 2016;11: e0161126.
 25. Kawabe K, Horiuchi F, Ochi M, Oka Y, Ueno S. Internet addiction: Prevalence and relation with mental states in adolescents. *Psychiatry Clin Neurosci* 2016; 70:405-12.
 26. Tsitsika A, Janikian M, Schoenmakers TM, Tzavela EC, Olafsson K, Wójcik S, et al. Internet addictive behavior in adolescence: a cross-sectional study in seven European countries. *Cyberpsychol Behav Soc Netw* 2014; 17:528-35.